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Data Management Plan

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Abstract

This Data Management Plan (DMP) describes the data management life cycle for the data to be collected, processed, and generated by the Horizon Europe eRImote project. It covers data formats such as text documents, presentations, tables, survey data, personal data, as well as information materials presented on the eRImote website. The first version of the DMP is submitted by month 4 of the project but is intended to function as a living document.

Table of Content

Introduction.....	4
1. Data Summary	5
2. FAIR data.....	6
2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata.....	6
2.2. Making data accessible.....	6
2.3. Making data interoperable.....	7
2.4. Increase data re-use	7
3. Allocation of resources.....	8
4. Data security.....	8
5. Ethics.....	9

Introduction

The EU project eRImote (European Research Infrastructures - Pathway to Improved Resilience and Digital and Remote Access) is the first to consider solutions for digital and remote service provision across RI domains and to look for transferable practices and new developments that will improve accessibility and resilience of RI infrastructures. While existing processes will be collected, eRImote will also explore new solutions using defined use cases to develop and test their implementation in RI scenarios.

The project's aims are:

- To build a foundation of knowledge, based on existing practises and RI responses to the COVID-19 pandemic, on the expansion and new implementation of remote and digital solutions for RI infrastructure access.
- To compile a public knowledge database including technologies, software and resilience strategies for remote/digital methodology annotated with examples of barriers, bottlenecks, future developments, investment and user experience.
- To provide a set of recommendations for RIs to foster further development of remote/digital infrastructure processes across all RI domains and implement first uses cases of new remote access methods.
- To reach out beyond the consortium and engage further RI stakeholders.

In realizing these aims within the project duration of 30 months (01 June 2022 – 30 November 2024), eRImote follows the principle of open science by pursuing an approach that is as open as possible and as closed as necessary. eRImote is dedicated to promoting FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable) data. In this sense, it devotes itself to adhering to best practices of handling survey data, document, source code and software.

Personal data of the project are dealt with in compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and an eRImote Data Privacy Policy was set up. Personal information is handled securely and financial information is kept confidential.

A Data Management Plan (DMP) is a key element of good data management as it is the initial tool to implement our FAIR data policy. The following paragraphs summarise the data types and address the FAIR principles applied to the data collected or generated by eRImote. Then, the DMP addresses resources, security and ethics.

This document follows the EC – Horizon Europe Data Management Plan template provided in the EC Funding & tender portal.

<https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/how-to-participate/reference-documents;programCode=HORIZON>

1. Data Summary

The eRImote consortium will identify strategies and solutions to enable the transition to more remote and digital access to RI services. Therefore, the project will gather information to identify current processes and practices in RI service delivery across different scientific domains which will be compiled in the publicly accessible eRImote Information Platform and will be published in the eRImote Green Paper. Therefore, documents (text, presentations, video recordings, tables) as well as personal and survey data sets will be generated within the project. The project will not generate scientific data like instruments do. In addition to raw and processed data, additional output of the project might include source codes and software.

The eRImote project will further re-use existing data where such data exists and is shared addressing our questions either from partners within the consortium or from the wider community. Such data, depending on content, could be used to compare or supplement the data gathered within the project, investigate trends over time, and ensure efficient use of resources without duplication of effort in producing e.g. training materials.

Table 1: Generated and collected data in eRImote.

Data Type	Origin	Expected data size	Contents
Text documents	Generated by individual partners and collaboration between partners	~ 100s Megabytes	Deliverables, meeting minutes, documentation
Presentations and video recordings	Generated by individual partners and collaboration between partners	~ 100s Megabytes	Dissemination material, presentations at meetings, workshops and conferences
Tables	Generated by partners, by gathering information within networks, from external stakeholders, workshops, expert groups and use cases	~ 100s Megabytes	Available methods, services at RIs concerning remote access, evaluation and recommendations of remote access services
Personal data	Generated by partners, by gathering information within networks, from external stakeholders, workshops, expert groups and use cases	~ 100s Megabytes	Contact information of consortium members, network contact persons, diverse stakeholders
Survey data	Generated by individual partners and collaboration between partners	100s Megabytes	Answers to surveys from different individuals
Source codes (if applicable)	Generated by individual partners and collaboration between partners	10s Megabytes	Extension of existing catalogues and data processing codes
Software (if applicable)	Generated by individual partners	~ 100s Megabytes	Software to store data sets

The collected data will be useful to the broader RI community from all ESFRI domains, as well as the core facility and scientific service provider community as a whole, and in a global context. The eRImote project will not only reach out to RI representatives but also to other stakeholders such as users, policymakers, funders and industry. By making the data publicly available via the eRImote Information Platform and the eRImote Green Paper, the different stakeholders may access and use the data for their own purpose. Data provided in the eRImote Information Platform and the eRImote Green Paper will be processed beforehand and will include, if any, minimal personal data.

2. FAIR data

eRImote is dedicated to promoting FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable) data.

2.1. Making data findable

Text documents, presentations, video recordings and tables produced as part of eRImote will adhere to a clear naming convention based on best practices. All project related documents will be assigned to a work package and will include document information as part of version control. Templates for presentations, deliverables and milestones are made available for all project participants.

Survey data will be stored with clear naming convention based on best practices as well. Processed data from surveys will follow clear rules for names of variables, values and coding. Data entries in the eRImote Information Platform will be tagged with keywords upon which data can be filtered to enhance findability/discoverability.

We will aim to have persistent identifiers for as much of the data as possible, via submission of final outputs, such as the Green Paper, to recognised archives providing Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) or via uploading project documents (at least public deliverables) on Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/>). Internal persistent identifiers, DOIs as well as versioning of documents will be used to allow discovery of data in the internal eRImote Data Storage as well as in the publicly available eRImote Information Platform.

2.2. Making data accessible

The curated data will be deposited in the trusted institutional repository provided by the partner Instruct-ERIC (ARIA Platform) and will be made available through the eRImote website.

The ARIA platform is developed and hosted by Instruct-ERIC which is the project partner performing the work of implementing the Information Platform therein within the eRImote project. Instruct-ERIC has track record of hosting ARIA software since 2014 including providing the software to external organisations and infrastructures.

The data will be assigned an internal identifier within ARIA. A single DOI will be assigned to the entire eRImote Information Platform via registering it within the created eRImote Zenodo community (<https://zenodo.org/communities/erimote/>) as a data set.

By using an institutional repository, data is securely stored ensuring sustainability of data. The repository provided by Instruct-ERIC helps long-term preservation of the data collected within the eRImote project. The partner is further in contact with the ERIC-Forum with the aim of providing a long-term storage and accessibility and to guarantee sustainability and usage of data even after the end of the project.

Data will be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol. For all personal data processed within the project the appropriate agreements (data privacy policy, data processing agreement, joint controller agreement) will be in place.

Not all data will be made openly available. The results from the remote access landscape analysis will be made available via the eRImote Information Platform which can be accessed via the project's website after data has been curated. The Green Paper will also be published with open access. Personal data including contact information will

not be made openly available but will be kept internally within the eRImote consortium and in the eRImote Internal Data Storage (Microsoft SharePoint) with restricted access rights only.

The data included in the eRImote Information Platform will contain information on RIs, remote service categories offered and solutions and recommendations concerning remote and digital access to RIs. The data will result from the eRImote activities, notably workshops, expert groups (WP3) and uses cases (WP4) as well as the mapping activities in WP5.

Downloads from the publicly available eRImote Information Platform do not require explicit personal identity information. However, cookies may be issued when visiting the platform. For the eRImote Internal Data Storage, an account is required to access the SharePoint which includes personal identity information.

Public deliverables will be made openly accessible via the eRImote community created on Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/communities/erimote/>) while confidential deliverables and materials will be securely stored in the project's collaboration space with restricted access rights, but accessible for all project participants (Microsoft SharePoint). By uploading the public project deliverables to Zenodo a DOI will be assigned to each document and they will be findable using the Zenodo search feature. Given their size, uploading the deliverables to Zenodo does not require previous arrangement. Anonymous access to public deliverables is guaranteed. For confidential deliverables, the identity will be ascertained using the SharePoint's credentials.

In line with the FAIR principles, documents will contain additional information on at least the following: author(s), title, date of publication, publication venue, Horizon Europe funding, project name, project acronym, project number, licensing terms and persistent identifiers (where applicable).

Data gathered and made available within eRImote will be accessible at least for 5 years after the final balance of the eRImote project as stated in grant agreement no. 101057557. It is considered as important to keep the data updated also after the project duration of 30 months and to ensure the accessibility. Therefore, one eRImote partner (Instruct-ERIC) is in contact with the ERIC-Forum for providing a long-term storage and accessibility and to guarantee sustainability and usage of data.

2.3. Making data interoperable

eRImote does not produce scientific data per se. However, eRImote contributes to making the collected data interoperable by applying best practices in documenting its data and by providing public access to the project results via the eRImote Information Platform (accessible via the website) and the eRImote Green Paper. The data can be re-used by different stakeholders.

The eRImote project will use standard vocabulary and ontologies where such are available, for example within the ESFRI domain established by projects such as CatRIS. If necessary, data will include qualified references to other data within the eRImote project. Qualified references will create meaningful links between data resources and will with that enrich the contextual knowledge about the data.

Discussions on how to make data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and beyond the project are still ongoing. Work Package 2 and 3 will come up with a solution on the rules to make data interoperable within the first six months of the project period and before data will be inserted in the eRImote Information Platform.

2.4. Increase data re-use

Data gathered in the remote access landscape analysis and via workshops and expert groups will be made openly available after processing to permit re-use by different stakeholders. eRImote intends to use open licences when making the data publicly available, such as Creative Commons licences (CC) BY 4.0 or equivalent.

By making the data accessible via the eRImote Information Platform and by publishing results in the eRImote Green Paper, data produced will be openly available and reusable for third parties. By seeking for a long-term accessibility for the eRImote Information Platform for more than 5 years after the final balance of the eRImote project and as the eRImote Green Paper will be available as legacy document, data will be available for third parties even after the end of the project. It is foreseen to gather all relevant project data and outputs in the eRImote Information Platform and the eRImote Green Paper.

The provenance of data collected within eRImote will be documented thoroughly. Most of the existing data provenance standards are domain-specific and do not map one-to-one to the data generated within the eRImote project. Therefore, we will follow as best as possible general standards and data will be allocated a persistent identifier or DOI, changes in all documents will be tracked and comprehensive version numbers applied, where applicable.

There is no restriction on use for all public eRImote deliverables uploaded in zenodo, which will be under Creative Commons licences (CC) BY 4.0. The access to confidential deliverables will be provided by the SharePoint collaboration space through nominative accounts for project participants.

All the project partners are responsible for and engaged in the data produced within the eRImote project. Data quality assurance procedures concern naming and versioning of documents. Comprehensible data storage within the eRImote Data Storage and the external eRImote Information Platform will be implemented. To ensure effective identification, documents should include the name of the project, if applicable the work package and the topic of the document. Furthermore, a version number should be added. Version numbers will be updated whenever a document is edited.

Different templates are provided in the eRImote Internal Data Storage (Microsoft SharePoint), e.g. templates for word documents and presentations as well as for reporting milestones and deliverables to ensure consistency and simplify re-use. In case of milestone and deliverable reports, the number of the respective milestone or deliverable has to be included in the title of the document for easy identification.

3. Allocation of resources

Existing infrastructures at the eRImote partners' institutes will be used to ensure that data are and remain FAIR as well as sustainable. Thanks to storing the data and various project materials via the eRImote Internal Data Storage at SharePoint hosted by Instruct-ERIC long term preservation of the project materials can be covered.

Incurring costs associated with data management, maintenance, and preservation are covered by the project budget.

In eRImote, WP1, under the lead of DESY, will be responsible for the general compliance of data management with respect to this DMP. The data repositories, the eRImote Internal Data Storage (Microsoft SharePoint) and the external eRImote Information Platform (ARIA platform) is managed and maintained by Instruct-ERIC, co-leader. WP leaders are responsible for the data management of their own products within their respective WP.

It is foreseen to make the eRImote Information Platform available for more than five years after the end of the eRImote project. To do so, long term preservation is discussed with the ERIC-Forum Instruct-ERIC is part of. Furthermore, the eRImote Green Paper as legacy document will be available in the long term and by that will preserve eRImote data.

4. Data security

An eRImote Data Privacy Policy was set up to inform on different aspects of data handling and processing. Data security issues are also addressed in the Data Privacy Policy.

For handling data as part of working collaboratively within the eRImote consortium, the responsibility lies with the individual partners. In extension to the eRImote Consortium Agreement a Data Processing Agreement was agreed on.

DESY and Instruct-ERIC as Joint Data Controllers within the project provide the infrastructure for project partners to work collaboratively via the eRImote Internal Data Storage hosted at Instruct-ERIC, thus creating a secure environment for international collaboration and knowledge exchange.

The data collected in eRImote will be stored internally in a data repository provided by Instruct-ERIC (Microsoft SharePoint hosted in the UK). Similarly, the external data repository is hosted by Instruct-ERIC (Aria Platform hosted in the UK). Data security for all documents uploaded to the Internal Data Storage and the eRImote Information platform relies on the security measures put in place by SharePoint and ARIA cloud service infrastructure.

5. Ethics

Personal data will be treated in compliance with GDPR. Some surveys have been and will be made in the framework of eRImote. Personal data collected for them will be deleted after anonymisation or aggregation. Other Personal Data collected, like contact lists of external stakeholders, the project's contact list file or lists of persons involved in workshops and other events, will be stored on the eRImote Internal Data Storage with restricted access, thereby accessible to project's participants only according to the GDPR.

The eRImote Data Privacy Policy describes the handling, processing and protection of Personal Data in detail. Personal data is not meant to be preserved for periods longer than 5 years after the final balance of the eRImote project.